

STUDY OF NITROGEN SYNTHESIZING PROPERTIES OF BACTERIA OF THE GENUS AZOTOBACTER

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Abstract; Azotobacters are N₂-synthesizing microorganisms that biosynthesize N₂ in a symbiotic relationship with plant roots. In this study, the importance of Azotobacter species was investigated in nitrogen assimilation activities of bacterial strains for biologically supplying plants with nitrogen through nitrogen-fixing bacteria and increasing soil fertility using natural bacteria. At certain concentrations of NaCl, phytohormonally active strains were observed to synthesize nitrogen like the control variants. When the salt concentration exceeded 200 mM, a significant decrease in acetylene reductase activity was observed in the strains. When the salinity exceeds 500 mM, it was observed that the ability of the strains to fix nitrogen was significantly reduced with a sharp decrease in the activity of acetylene reductase.

Keywords. Azotobacter, N₂-synthesis, microorganisms, plant roots, symbiotic, biological, free nitrogen in the air, nitrogen fixer, biological nitrogen supply to plants, nitrogen assimilation activities of bacterial strains, NaCl concentrations, phytohormone, active strain, nitrogen synthesis as options activity of acetylene reductase was observed.

The main biological feature of bacteria of the genus Azotobacter is their ability to synthesize atmospheric nitrogen. However, a decrease in the activity of acetylene reductase is observed in the cell under various adverse stress conditions (4). It is known that stress, especially saline and alkaline environments, has a negative effect on acetylene reductase activities (1,2). However, in order for the bacteria of the genus Azotobacter to have normal nitrogen assimilation activity in relatively unfavorable conditions, they should be adapted to stressful conditions (5,3).

In these experiments, we investigated the effect of salt stress on acetylene-reductase activities of active Azotobacter strains that were able to survive in different salinity conditions in previous studies. Observations were carried out at different concentrations of NaCl, and the nitrogen uptake activities of the strains were analyzed. The acetylene reductase activities of the strains varied in Ashby's liquid medium containing different concentrations of NaCl. *A. chroococcum* X2018, *A. chroococcum* A2018, *A. vinelandii* A9, *A. vinelandii* A13 showed

acetylene-reductase activity at relatively low concentrations of salinity, as in salt-free environments, but with increasing salt content in the environment, acetylene-reductase activity decreased.

In experiments, at relatively low concentrations of salinity, *A. chroococcum* X2018 and *A. vinelandii* A13 strains retained an average of 76–80% acetylene-reductase activity, while the average acetylene-reductase activity was 70–75% when the concentration of NaCl exceeded 100 mM. When the salt concentration was 200–400 mM, the acetylene reductase activity in the strains was equal to 45–60%. When the concentration of salt in the medium exceeds 500 mM, a sharp decrease in the activity of acetylene reductase was observed. At this concentration of salt, the activity of acetylene reductase averaged 34-37% (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Effect of NaCl on the acetylene-reductase activity of active *Azotobacter* strains.

For example, the acetylene-reductase activity of the *A. chroococcum* X2018 strain at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 mM of salinity was 2260, 2220, 2100, 2050, and 1850.0 nmol/vial/day, respectively. was equal, in *A. vinelandii* C21 strain, this indicator was 2500, 2450, 2300, 2250 and 2200 nmol/vial/day, respectively.

It can be concluded from the experiments that at certain concentrations of NaCl, phytohormonally active strains were able to fix nitrogen as well as the control variants. When the salt concentration exceeded 200 mM, a significant decrease in

acetylene reductase activity was observed in the strains. When the salinity exceeds 500 mM, it was observed that the ability of the strains to fix nitrogen was significantly reduced with a sharp decrease in the activity of acetylene reductase.

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